

Studies in the Anthraquinone Series. Synthesis of 1:6-Dihydroxy-and 1:7-Dihydroxy-3-methyl-anthraquinones.

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Of the three dihydroxyanthraquinones of the emodin type (Mitter and Biswas, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 770) only two namely, 1:8-dihydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone (chrysophanic acid) and 6:8-dihydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone (Marchlewski, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 1142), are known and it appeared to us of interest to synthesise 1:6-dihydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone.

Emodin.

Chrysophanic acid.

6:8-Dihydroxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone.

1:6-Dihydroxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone.

The synthesis can be effected by the condensation of 4-nitrophthalic anhydride with *m*-cresol in presence of aluminium chloride (*cf.* Eder and Widmer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 5, 6). A mixture of two benzoylbenzoic acids is obtained which can be separated by fractional crystallisation. One of these (A) melts at 196° and the other (B) at 202.3°.

(I)

(II)

When phthalic anhydride or a substituted phthalic anhydride is condensed with a phenol, the condensation takes place in the *ortho* or *para* position to a hydroxyl group and we have therefore four possible formulae for the resulting products.

When the acid (A) melting at 196° is fused with caustic potash, a mixture of *p*-nitrobenzoic acid and an acid which gives a violet coloration with ferric chloride is obtained. Similarly from (B) is obtained a mixture of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid and an acid which gives a violet coloration with ferric chloride. The formation of the second acid, a derivative of salicylic acid, eliminates (III) and (IV). The constitution of the benzoylbenzoic acids (A) and (B) are therefore (I) and (II) respectively.

On reduction with ferrous sulphate and ammonia, (I) gave 4-amino-(2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid, m.p. 218°, from which on diazotisation 4-hydroxy-(2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid, m.p. 214-15°, was obtained. This, on ring-closure, gave 1:7-dihydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone, m.p. 255-56° (V).

Similarly from (II), 5-amino-(2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid, m.p. 237-38°, 5-hydroxy-(2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid, m.p. 255-56°, and 1:6-dihydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone (VII), m.p. 213-14°, were obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Nitrophthalic anhydride.—This is prepared by the method of Bogert and Boroschek (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, **23**, 743) with some modifications (Mitter and Sarkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 619).

Condensation of nitrophthalic anhydride with m-cresol.—The anhydride (10 g.) is suspended in *m*-cresol (100 c.c.) and to this powdered aluminium chloride (20 g.) is added in small portions at a time in the course of one hour (oil-bath at 100-10°). When the addition is complete the temperature is raised to 130° and maintained at that temperature for 3-4 hours, the mixture being

mechanically stirred throughout. The contents of the flask are then acidified with 10 p.c. hydrochloric acid (135 c.c.) and the excess of *m*-cresol removed by steam distillation. The residue is digested with calcium carbonate, filtered and acidified with hydrochloric acid when a plastic mass is obtained. This is dissolved in hot methyl alcohol (charcoal) and filtered. On cooling, 4-nitro-(2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid, m.p. 196°, crystallises out in needles, yield, 3 g. (Found: N, 4.55. $C_{15}H_{11}O_6N$ requires N, 4.65 per cent.).

A mixture of the acid (2 g.), caustic potash (10 g.) and a few drops of water is heated in a silver crucible to about 215° for 20 minutes. When cold, the mass is dissolved in water, filtered, acidified and the precipitate washed with water. It is then digested with calcium carbonate, filtered, acidified and the precipitate crystallised from water. The residue is then distilled in steam until the distillate ceases to give a violet coloration with ferric chloride, which it does in the beginning. The residue melts at 238° and the melting point is not depressed on admixture with *p*-nitrobenzoic acid. The condensation product is therefore 4-nitro-(2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid.

5-Nitro-(2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl) 2-benzoic acid (II).—The methyl alcoholic mother liquor from the preparation of (I) is evaporated and repeatedly crystallised from glacial acetic acid until its melting point becomes constant at 202.3°. It crystallises in needles. (Found: N, 4.61. $C_{15}H_{11}O_6N$ requires N, 4.65 per cent.).

On alkali fusion, the acid (II) gives *m*-nitrobenzoic acid and an acid which gives a violet coloration with ferric chloride.

4-Amino-(2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid.—Freshly prepared ferrous sulphate (32 g.) is dissolved in water (210 c.c.), boiled and concentrated ammonia (50 c.c.) then added. To the precipitated ferrous hydroxide a warm solution of the nitroacid (4.5 g.) in concentrated ammonia (45 c.c.) is added, and the mixture boiled for 15 minutes. The filtrate is boiled to drive off ammonia and to the boiling solution, a hot solution of alum (4.5 g.) in water (45 c.c.) is gradually added and the whole filtered hot when the amino-acid crystallises out. It crystallises from alcohol in prisms melting at 218° with evolution of gas. (Found: N, 5.1. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 5.2 per cent.).

4-Hydroxy-(2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid.—The amino acid (2 g.) is dissolved in dilute ammonia by warming and dilute

hydrochloric acid added until the precipitate first formed redissolves. The bright yellow solution of the hydrochloride is cooled to 0° and while stirring continuously by a mechanical stirrer, the calculated quantity of a solution of sodium nitrite (0.7 g.) in water (7 c.c.) is gradually added. The precipitated diazonium salt is decomposed by boiling for 15 to 20 minutes, a little animal charcoal added and the whole filtered hot, when the hydroxy acid separates in silky crystals. It is recrystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum ether. Rectangular plates, m.p. $214-15^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 65.9; H, 4.1. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.2; H 4.4 per cent.).

1:7-Dihydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone.—To the hydroxy acid (2 g.) is added boric anhydride (2 g.) and sulphuric acid (*d*, 1.84, 4 c.c.) and then fuming sulphuric acid (20 g., 20 p.c. SO_3). The mixture is heated on the water-bath for three hours and then poured on to crushed ice when an orange mass is obtained. This is first extracted with boiling water to remove boric acid and then with cold 5 p. c. solution of sodium carbonate. The crude anthraquinone on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave bright yellow silky needles melting at $255-56^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 70.5; H, 2.7. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70.9; H 3.9 per cent.).

5-Amino-(2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid.—The acid is obtained by reducing (II) exactly in the same manner as (I). Prisms from water, m.p. $237-38^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 5.2 per cent.).

5-Hydroxy-(2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid.—The amino acid is diazotised as in the case of 4-amino-(2 hydroxy-4-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid. Rectangular plates from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. $215^{\circ}-16^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 66.3; H, 4.2. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.2; H, 4.4 per cent.).

1:6-Dihydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone.—The ring closure is done exactly as in the case of 1:7-dihydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone. Bright yellow silky needles from glacial acetic acid, m.p. $213^{\circ}-14^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 70.6; H, 3.6. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70.9; H, 3.9 per cent.).